

Implication of New Education Policy in Covid-19 Pandemic and its impact on Teacher Education

Dr. Mohd. Talib Ather Ansari

Assistant Professor, MANUU, College of Teacher Education, Bidar (Karnataka)

Abstract

The New Education Policy 2020 aims to reform the educational structure by taking into account different factors such as the experiences of different groups and individuals. It is a progressive shift that will bring India on par with the world's leading countries in education. Everyone involved in the education system will be affected by the changes proposed in the new education policy. Following the WHO's statement that "COVID-19 will not be disappear in the near future", many people are thinking of ways to live together with the pandemic. This paper aims to discuss the various challenges that the pandemic has created on Teacher education in India. The coronavirus pandemic has affected over 210 countries since it started. It has caused severe shortages of essential supplies and services across the globe. In India, the situation has severely affected the country's economy. COVID-19 has an adverse impact on the education system in India. It has raised many concerns about the existing infrastructure of teacher education.

Keywords: COVID-19, NEP-2020, Coronavirus Pandemic, UGC, Teacher Education, NCTE, Digitalization

Introduction

India started its journey with various obstacles in its path. This included poverty, casteism, and religion. Education is a key component to develop a country like India. Fortunately, the UN declared the Right to Education as a Human Right, which means that every child from 6 to 14 years old is entitled to free and compulsory education. This right was introduced in India on April 1, 2010. In 2020, we introduced various programs and policies to improve the educational system in India. One of these is the National Education Policy 2020. This policy aims to create a new educational system in India by 2030.

The Indian education sector has been severely affected by the covid-19 pandemic. Since April 2020, educational institutions in the country have been temporarily closed. The continuous national

lockdowns, which started from April 2020, have affected the education system in the country. The Centre and the states are working towards overcoming the effects of the lockdowns. During this period, we try to maintain the regularity and quality of education and learning in both urban and rural areas. Through online learning, we aim to create a comprehensive learning environment for the students. These advanced learning initiatives are very popular among various groups such as students, teachers, and policymakers. As India prepares for the New Indian Digitalized era, it needs to implement effective and efficient teaching-learning methods to bridge the gap caused by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Changes from New Education Policy-2020

The National Education Policy-2020 was approved by the Indian government to improve

the education system in the country. This comprehensive policy aims to introduce a 5+3+3+4 structure in the education system.

Fig. 1: Prepared by the author

Teacher Education

Teacher education and training is a mandatory component of higher education in India to ensure that the quality of teaching is maintained. There are various teacher education programs available in different universities in India. Most of the universities and colleges in the country have their own Department or School of Education, which is responsible for training quality teachers at various levels. In the present scenario of teacher higher education in India UGC the governing body of Indian education, Ministry of Human Resource and Development of India issued the directions to University Grant Commission, under section 20-(1) of the UGC Act, 1956, from its wide order time to time where MHRD and UGC emphasize quality and quantity of teacher education. The objectives of the new education policy-2020 are defined to ensure that all primary, secondary and higher education students are taught by motivation, passionate, highly qualified, professionally trained, and well-equipped teachers. In this regard, the responsibility of teacher education is more difficult because NEP-2020 further emphasizes on teacher education and stated that

"Teachers truly shape the futures of our children - and, therefore, the future of our nation. It is through teachers that our children are imparted with values, knowledge, empathy, creativity, ethics, life skills, and social responsibility. Teachers

thus form the very heart of the education process, and represent an indispensable vehicle towards a progressive, just, educated, and prosperous society." NEP-2020

Present Scenario of Teacher education in India

Fig. 2: Prepared by the author

The National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) will be developed by the NCTE under the guidelines of NEP-2020. New Education Policy-2020 set a common guidelines to establish NPST (National Professional Standards for Teachers) that will be developed till the end of 2022, by the NCTE (National Council for Teacher Education), A governing body of Indian Teacher Education, under the guidelines of newly established GEC (General Education Council), A proposed governing body to look into the affair of overall educational standard in collaboration with NCERT(National Council of Educational Research and Training), A centralized body to govern secondary education across India, SCERTs (State council of educational research and training), A state governing body to control secondary level of education at concerned state, and include all teachers communities from all-regions and all educational levels i.e. primary, secondary, university including professional education to provide their thoughts and expertise to develop teachers preparation courses in its restructured new form as PSSB (Professional Standard Setting Body), that cover all teacher preparation programme and courses at all levels according to NEP-2020

Objectives of NEP-2020 for Teacher Education

The new education policy, which was released in 2020, aims to improve the teaching profession by establishing a set of goals and strategies that can be implemented efficiently.

- (a) Teachers must develop their skills and standards according to the National Performance Standards for Teachers.
- (b) Teachers will have to continuously improve themselves and adopt new practices in education.
- (c) The qualities that make a good teacher are related to the course of studies and the communities where they work.
- (d) It is the goal of the teacher to deliver a high-quality teaching and learning experience that is enjoyable and motivating for the students.
- (e) To ensure that educational establishments and schools have the necessary resources to implement and use new technologies related to Information and Communication Technology (ICT).
- (f) Teachers should be engaged in learning activities in their subject areas and should not be overworked.
- (g) autonomy is a must for teachers to implement their own unique teaching style and methods.
- (h) The teachers will have to keep up with the latest developments in their subject and pedagogy.
- (i) It is also ensured that teachers are actively involved in the communities they serve.
- (j) The School Complex Management Committee will establish a culture that is inclusive, caring, collaborative, and committed to achieving excellence in education.
- (k) The motivation of teachers should be based on their performance and merits. It should also be evaluated on a clear and well-defined structure.

Expansion of COVID-19, in India

The current scenario of COVID-19 in India is a part of the trauma caused by SARS-CoV-2

disease. The first confirmed case of the disease was detected in Kerala on January 30, 2020. Since then, India has been witnessing steady waves of covid-19 cases. As of September 2020, India has become the second-highest confirmed case in the world. In August 2020, India recorded the highest single-day spike in COVID-19 cases, with over 80,000 cases. On March 22, 2020, a 14-hour curfew was imposed in India, which is followed by continuous nationwide lockdowns to prevent the spread of COVID-19 disease.

First wave Nationwide Centralized lockdowns in India:

- (a) First Lockdown (21 days): from 25th March 2020 to 14th April 2020
- (b) Second Lockdown (19days): from 15th April 2020 to 3rd May 2020
- (c) Third Lockdown (14days): from 04th May 2020 to 17th May 2020
- (d) Fourth Lockdown (14days): from 18th May 2020 to 31st May 2020

Unlocking in different phases after 1st Wave:

The Ministry of Home and Family welfare has issued fresh guidelines for the re-opening of the country in June 2020. The guidelines suggest that the re-opening of the country will be carried out in various phases starting from June 2020. All areas in red/conclusion zones will have to be locked down after June 8. These will allow the local and other activities to be conducted in phases, but educational activities were not permitted in-person.

- (a) First Phase of reopening (30days): from 01st June 2020 to 30th June-2020.
- (b) Second Phase of reopening (31days): from 01st July 2020 to 31st July-2020.
- (c) Third Phase of reopening (31days): from 01st August 2020 to 31st August-2020.
- (d) Fourth Phase of reopening (30days): from 01st September 2020 to 30th September-2020.
- (e) Fifth Phase of reopening (unlimited): from 01st October onwards resuming educational activities.

Unlock 5.0: 1 October 2020 –Resuming Educational Activities:

The Central and State governments have issued various notifications for unlocking India. These notifications include setting up of autonomous state governments and managing and implementing unlocking activities with an eye on 26 protocols. To implement the procedures, schools and educational institutions have been asked to re-open on September 21, 2020. The various processes and guidelines related to the Unlock 4 and the Unlock 5.0 have been implemented across the country. In days to come, these guidelines will be followed to enable schools and colleges to resume their safe educational activities in-person and online.

Covid-19, Second wave, and Nationwide lockdowns in India again:

After learning about the coronavirus pandemic, Indian citizens started to panic as it quickly spread and captured all parts of the country. Peoples in rural areas and cities witnessed very tough situations due to the disease's spread. Many peoples also died due to the collapsing medical facilities and cremation spots. In India, the number of covid-19 cases has increased significantly even in rural areas. This was the indication of the second wave of covid-19 that started in the country and affected various regions. As a result, all the state and union territories imposed various restrictions to control the spread of the disease. During the second wave of covid-19, which started on May 19, 2021, over four lakh cases of positive cases were reported on a daily basis, making it the most dangerous wave in India. India is the first country in the world to implement the covid-19 vaccine. As of July 2021, there have been over 31,000 confirmed cases of this deadly disease in the country. Over 390 million doses of vaccine have been administered to India's population since the start of the immunization drive. This is a positive sign that the vaccine campaign is successfully protecting the country's population.

Planning to re-opening Educational Activities again

(a) Schools and colleges of green and orange zones shall be allowed to re-open from August/September-2021.

- (b) Central and State Universities, Higher Educational Institutions, the examination conducting bodies and centers may plan to re-opening all educational activities with covid protocols and all safety measures, overcrowding should be prohibited.
- (c) To resume educational activities teaching and non-teaching in-person presence should be reduced to 50%, and students will also be called on rotation bases, online teaching and learning, Blended learning, teleconferencing, and related work must be restored and continue.
- (d) Students from 9th to 12th will have the choice to attend classes in-person or virtually/online with prior permission to parents, teachers, and school administrators.
- (e) In classrooms covid protocols must be followed accordingly, maintaining 6 feet distancing, wearing a mask, overcrowding must be discouraged, proper health and hygiene measures should be added in covid protocols.
- (f) All necessary school and college activities like sports meet, assemblies, and other overcrowding activities are strictly banned till the situation is normalized.
- (g) All schools will display covid help-line numbers of local health officials to contact in an emergency.
- (h) All teachers/students and other office staff must cover their faces is mandatory.
- (i) Proper sanitization of the classrooms and frequent hand washing and use of alcohol-based sanitizer must be done frequently on a priority basis.
- (j) All teachers and students must be followed respiratory etiquettes, coughing, sneezing, with a tissue/hanky/flexed elbow, and dispose of used tissues properly.
- (k) Besides this, vaccination drives in Schools, Colleges, and Universities should be done within the stipulated time. All teachers and students ensure the use of the *Aarogya Setu Covid-19* mobile application wherever possible.

MHRD and UGC taking initiatives

The Ministry of Human Resources Development and the Universities of India have been working together to improve the quality of education in the country. They have also taken various initiatives such as to develop and implement the National Vocational Educational Qualification Framework (NVEQF). Besides this, the MHRD and UGC are also working towards establishing a strong link between higher education and the Inter-University Centre for Teacher Education. The UGC has also created career-oriented courses in various natural sciences, arts, commerce and humanities through online mode for train university teachers.

In May 2020, the UGC has issued a circular regarding the implementation of Blended learning in Higher educational institutions. All these initiatives of various educational governing bodies are very helpful in promoting technology in education. In this pandemic, the use of technologies in education may be beneficial and emphasize the various modes of learning that are available through E-Learning platforms.

Challenges of present trauma for revamping Educational Activities.

Reopening educational institutions and educational activities during this covid 19 pandemic is a big challenge, but we did not block the young guns because this is our national future for economic and social productivities to develop the nation. Due to the various lockdowns in the education and learning field, the UGC has set up an expert committee to review the matter. The committee issued various major issues like examination calendar, admission, promotions, etc. The reopening of Higher education institutions is subject to various conditions.

Since educational activities have resumed following the implementation of COVID-19 Pandemic, many questions arise regarding the safety measures taken to ensure the continuity of educational activities in the classrooms. We may also follow the safety measures mentioned by the MHFW. We need to improve the infrastructure

facilities and provide an online learning environment to support and attract young talent for teacher education in India. We need to renovate our infrastructure facilities and provide an online learning environment to deliver a quality education and develop a robust teaching-learning curriculum.

Conclusion

Indian teacher training programs have made great strides in quality and quantity in the past years. However, there are still many areas where they need to be strengthened, such as those related to technology-based teaching-learning process, blended learning, and flipped learning. In the near future, schools and colleges will start implementing digitalized learning strategies and methods. This will allow teachers to provide personalized learning solutions that will enhance the learning experience of their students. digitalized learning is very beneficial for students as it eliminates the need for time-bond activities and it allows students to focus on the learning instead of on physical appearances. It saves students time and money.

During the pandemic, it is difficult to develop and implement digitalized learning platforms in every college and school in India. This is due to the lack of funds and expertise in this area. This e-learning and Blended learning environment should be established first in the training institutions that are providing pre-service teachers training. These institutions should also have their own e-learning infrastructure. Also, the use of digital resources such as social media and movies can create a dropout rate of up to 30% in the school due to the lack of controlled study atmosphere. Creating a well-defined and purposeful digitalized curriculum is a major step towards providing comprehensive and continuous educational opportunities to the students in this pandemic phase. With the use of digital learning, we can provide an alternative method of education to the traditional system of education in India, which can meet the needs of the hour. Through digitalized learning, India's educational institutions must ensure that their

students are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to face the challenges of the 21st century. This platform can help improve the quality of education in the country and also safeguard the institution's operations during times of pandemic.

References

1. Planning Commission Annual Report, (2005). *GOI National Knowledge Commission Report to the Nation 2006-09*. retrieved on 25.03.2021, Available at <https://www.aicte-india.org/downloads/nkc.pdf>
2. Flahault, A., Siddiqui, A. F., Wiederkehr, M., & Rozanova, L. (2020). The situation of India in the COVID-19 Pandemic: India's Initial Pandemic Experience. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(23), 8994. available at <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17238994>
3. Government of India Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Directorate General of Health Services (EMR Division), (2020). *Final SOP on the partial resumption of activities in schools from September-2020*. retrieved on 10.09.2020 Available at: <https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/FinalSOPonpartialresumptionofactivitiesinschools8092020.pdf>
4. Hindustan Times, Web desk Correspondent (2020). *India's case count crosses 100,000, Delhi eases restrictions: Covid-19 news today*. Hindustan Times, 19th May 2020, P.07, Retrieved on 20 May 2020. Available at <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/india-s-case-count-crosses-100-000-delhi-eases-restrictions-covid-19-news-today/story-rF9hpAOpOKoKPF8CKQ99N.html>
5. India Today, Web desk (2021). *Coronavirus outbreak*. India Today, Daily News Paper -April, 17-2021, pp.02-05, retrieved on 25.07.2021 available at <https://www.indiatoday.in/coronavirus-outbreak/story/full-list-of-lockdown-curfews-across-india-1791896-2021-04-17>
6. MHFW, Government of India, guidelines. "SOP" (Standard Operating Procedure), retrieved on 10.09.2020, Available at <https://www.mohfw.gov.in/>
7. Ministry of Human Resource and Development Gov. of India (2019-20). *Draft NEW Education Policy, Revised*. In (2020), Retrieved on 16/07/2020 available at https://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Draft_NEP_2019_EN_Revised.pdf
8. Nathan. T.N., (2020). *India's COVID-19 cases world's 2nd highest*. Times of India, Sep 6, 2020, pp. 01-2. Available at <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/indias-covid-cases-worlds-2nd-highest/articleshow/77956328.cms>
9. National Policy on Education, (1986) Government of India Programme of Action Ministry of HRD (1992) *Framework of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2002)* 11th Five Year Plan.
10. Sain. S.K & Kaware, S.S. (2014). The Challenges and Quality of Teacher Education in India at Present in Indian Educational Scenario. *Journal of Education & Social Policy*, Vol. 1 No. 1; June 2014, Pg. No.13-17, Retrieved on 17/05/2020, Available at http://jespnet.com/journals/Vol_1_No_1_June_2014/3.pdf Retrieved on 17/05/2019
11. Sinha, R., Ganatra, V. & Pandey, P., et.al (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on Business Performance: A Case Study of Starbucks. *International Journal of Tourism & Hospitality in Asia Pasific*, Vol 4, No 2 (2021), E-ISSN:2654-7945, ISSN:2685-8800
12. Suyog, (2020, July 12). *National Policy on Education III* <https://dixitsuyog.wordpress.com/2019/07/12/national-education-policy-iii/> Retrieved on 09.09.2020
13. The Indian Express, Web desk (2021). *India Covid-19: Second wave*. The Indian Express, Daily News Paper -July, 25-2021, retrieved on 25.07.2021 available at <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/covid-19-second-wave-heres-a-list-of-states-that-have-imposed-lockdowns-7306634/>
14. Vijay Nitin (2020). Global pandemic COVID-19: Influence and planning for Indian Education System. *Higher Education Digest*, 21st September-2020 available at <https://www.highereducationdigest.com/global-pandemic-covid-19-influence-and-planning-for-indian-education-system/>
15. Worldometers.inf. Web desk, (2020). *India, Coronavirus Cases*. Retrieved on 10.09.2020 available at <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/country/india/>
16. Worldometers.inf. Web desk, (2021). *India, Coronavirus Cases*. Retrieved on 25.07.2021 available at <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/country/india/>